

LINGUISTIC STATUS OF PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract: *This article explores the linguistic status of paremiological units, particularly proverbs, within various linguistic and cultural contexts. It examines the role of proverbs as a universal phenomenon in folklore across different languages, emphasizing their cultural and communicative significance. The study addresses the semantic and structural characteristics of proverbs, their stability in syntactic form, and their complex interplay with related linguistic phenomena such as sayings, aphorisms, and proverbial phraseologisms. The article highlights various theoretical perspectives, including A. Nosirov's categorization of proverbs within the phraseological inventory and the influence of communication contexts on their pragmatic meanings. Additionally, the article explores the broader implications of proverbs in reflecting national worldviews and their linguistic functions, such as their ability to convey both literal and figurative meanings. The article further discusses the complexities of translating proverbs across languages and their retention of meaning and structure in different cultural settings. Finally, the work draws on the ideas of notable linguists like A.I. Kunin, Georges Milner, and Sh. Balli to present proverbs as fixed expressions with a symmetrical relationship between form and meaning, underscoring their importance in the structure of language.*

Keywords: *Paremiological units, proverbs, phraseologisms, cultural significance, structural characteristics, pragmatic meaning, communication context, interlingual translation.*

Introduction

The fact that proverbs, as examples of folk literature, are a common phenomenon across all linguistic cultures can be demonstrated by their widespread study in various countries. Proverbs in different languages are collected and analyzed systematically in terms of their genesis, semantic and structural characteristics, and their role in speech activities. However, the linguistic status of proverbs and their relationship with related phenomena are viewed differently. The primary cultural source of language units is considered to be the realities that encompass the surrounding world. These include myths, legends, comparative imagery, folklore, customs, religion, literature, and historical and political events [Ashurova D.U., "Vneshinvestprom," Tashkent – 2021.-38, 48].

Most researchers place proverbs within the folklore system, acknowledging their distinct status, while some interpret proverbs and sayings as units of the linguistic phraseological inventory. For example, in A. Nosirov's doctoral dissertation, proverbs, along with sayings, wise words, aphorisms, and popular expressions, are all categorized as proverbial phraseologisms (Nosirov 2016). Indeed, proverbs, like other fixed phraseological units, exhibit a characteristic of stability in their structure, meaning that altering their syntactic pattern presents challenges.

It is well-known that the famous phraseologist A.I. Kunin defined fixed forms as expressions that have specific characteristics and are used in speech in a ready-made form, making it difficult to imagine them fulfilling any communicative-pragmatic function outside

of the discourse context. The meaning of a proverb, however, is shaped by the speaker's communicative goals and the specific context, thus giving rise to pragmatic content and allowing for the expression of ideas in an indirect, expressive manner.

Proverbs, sayings, and aphorisms, as syntactic structures, are recognized by many scholars as having textual characteristics. Most of these researchers propose calling such units "communicative phrasemes" (Granger, Paquot 2008-42). In these structures, the speaker conveys broader ideas through a specific phraseme. By using such phrasemes, the speaker aims to persuade the listener of the validity of the message.

Moreover, the use of the term "multiword expressions" for these structures also indicates their status as complex speech units (Milder 2010). Proverbs are linguistic constructions that reflect the linguistic worldview and carry national cultural significance, with their worldview presented in an image-based form.

These structures are syntactically complete and semantically meaningful, reflecting the lifestyle of the community. According to A. Nosirov, the Western term "proverb" is derived from the Latin word "proverbium," which expresses concise ideas based on the life experience and surprising conclusions of the people. The scholar also notes that the Uzbek term "maqol" (proverb) originates from the Arabic word "qavlun" (to speak), referring to expressions of folk wisdom, and is used as a term for one of the aphoristic genres, meaning "a well-said word, phrase, or expression" (Nosirov 2016:15).

It is known that in phraseological units, meaning shifts occur, and the individual words may lose their original literal meanings or become entirely figurative. In contrast, words in proverbs often retain their core meaning, or both the literal and figurative meanings can coexist.

The figurative meaning in a proverb is related to its full context and defines its value, allowing communication participants to understand its meaning. Proverbs are often used to explain current situations by referencing past events. At the same time, the original meaning of a proverb is so clear that communication participants can easily understand and translate it. This can be observed in the interlingual equivalents and adoption of proverbs across languages.

Foreign linguists emphasize that proverbs are fixed combinations that carry meaning and retain their structure and form. They stress that the meaning and form of proverbs should not be overlooked. This is evident in the definition provided by French scholar Georges Milner in his article "The Structure of Proverbial Fixed Expressions," which states: "The distinguishing characteristic of proverbial expressions is that they have a symmetric link between meaning and form. That is, the meaning of a proverbial expression performs a specific function, and the symmetry of the form reflects the symmetry of the meaning" (Milne 1964:54, cited in Nasriddinova 2019:16).

The phraseologist Sh. Balli, who described the structural and semantic peculiarities of phraseological units, noted the equivalence of such units to words. However, the syntactic structure of a proverb does not fully align with the criteria established by French linguists. The structural-semantic peculiarity of a proverb lies in its ability to express a complete thought, which complicates its inclusion in the phraseological inventory of language.

REFERENCES

1. Ashurova, D.U. (2021). *Vneshinvestprom*, Tashkent, 38, 48.
2. Granger, S., & Paquot, M. (2008). *Phraseology: An Interdisciplinary Perspective*. John Benjamins Publishing Company.
3. Kunin, A.I. (1970). *Phraseology of the Russian Language*. Progress Publishers.
4. Milner, Georges. (1964). "The Structure of Proverbial Fixed Expressions." *Nasriddinova, 2019:16*.
5. Milder, A. (2010). *Multiword Expressions and their Role in Communication*.
6. Nosirov, A. (2016). *The Proverbs and Sayings in Linguistic and Cultural Contexts*.
7. Balli, Sh. (Year of publication needed). *The Structural and Semantic Peculiarities of Phraseological Units*.